

Hepatoprotective and antioxidant activity of aqueous extract of *Amorphophallus commutatus* var. *wayanadensis*

Sreena Raj and K. M. Gothandam*

School of Biosciences and Technology, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : gothandam@yahoo.com

Abstract : *Amorphophallus commutatus* var. *wayanadensis* is a red listed medicinal plant which has been used traditionally in Wayanad, India for various ailments like hemorrhoids and tumors. The hepatoprotective and antioxidant activity of aqueous extract of *Amorphophallus commutatus* var. *wayanadensis* (AEAC) was evaluated against carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄) induced hepatotoxicity in swiss albino mice models. Hepatoprotective potential of AEAC was determined by estimating the levels of hepatic marker enzymes and histopathological studies. Antioxidant activity of the extract was estimated using antioxidant enzyme activities and lipid peroxidation in the liver samples. AEAC showed significant reduction in the hepatic marker enzymes in the serum samples and increased the antioxidant enzyme activities compared to the CCl₄ group. Histopathological analysis also confirmed the hepatoprotective activity of the extract. Qualitative phytochemical screening revealed the presence of saponins as major phytoconstituent, which might be responsible for the hepatoprotective and antioxidant activity of the extract.

Keywords : Hepatoprotective, antioxidant, saponin, CCl₄ toxicity.

Introduction

Oxidative stress indicates the imbalance between free radical generated in the living system and the detoxification process. Highly reactive oxygen and nitrogen species thus generated in involved in the pathophysiology of various diseases including cancer, cardiovascular diseases, neuro-degenerative diseases and so on¹. Biological systems have endogenous antioxidant defensive mechanism to protect the body from the oxidative stress. Failure of the antioxidant enzyme to detoxify the free radical leads to oxidative stress. Intake of foods rich in natural antioxidant protects the body from the free radical generates disorders. *Amorphophallus commutatus* var. *wayanadensis* is an edible medicinal plant with wide range of pharmacological activities². The tubers of this traditional medicinal is used for various diseases like mouth diseases and piles³, scabies⁴ and as antidote for snake bit⁵ also traditionally used among the tribal communities of Wayanad for hemorrhoids. Even though this plant has significant pharmacological activities, till date no experimental studies have been done to validate its ethnobotanical uses. The present study is to explore the antioxidant and hepatoprotective activity of aqueous extract of

Amorphophallus commutatus var. *wayanadensis* (AEAC) against CCl₄ induced hepatic damage in mice models.

Experimental

Plant collection and extraction :

The plant material was collected from Wayanad and authenticated by Abdul Jaleel, Sir Syed College, Kerala and the herbarium was prepared and stored for further reference. The tubers were washed thoroughly and chopped into small pieces, air dried for two weeks. The extraction was done in a soxhlet apparatus using distilled water. After extraction the extract was concentrated using lyophilizer and stored at 4 °C for further studies.

Phytochemical analysis :

Qualitative phytochemical screening was performed according to the methods by Harborne⁹ with slight modifications.

Experimental procedure :

Swiss albino mice of either sex (20–25 g) were procured from VIT University animal house and all the experimental procedures were approved by the ethical committee of VIT University, India. The experimental protocol was performed according to the method of Lu *et al.*¹⁰

with slight modification. Six animals were grouped into five groups. Group I considered as control group received 0.9% saline for 15 days. Group II served as CCl₄ treated group received only 0.9% saline during the experimental period. Group III and IV served as experimental groups received aqueous extracts orally at a dosage of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg respectively. Group V (standard group) received standard drug silymarin orally at a dosage of 100 mg/kg for 15 days. All the groups except Group I received intra peritoneal injection of 0.2% CCl₄ in olive oil on day 15 one hour after treatment. Control group received olive oil on day 15th after treatment. After 24 h all the animals were sacrificed by cervical dislocation and blood and livers were collected for further studies.

Hepatoprotective activity of AEAC :

The hepatoprotective activity of the extract was determined by estimating the levels of hepatic marker enzymes in the serum samples. The levels of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) alkaline phosphatase (ALP) aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and bilirubin content was determined spectroscopically (GeneQuant 1300, GE Healthcare, UK) using kits from Euro Diagnostics Pvt. Ltd., India. The hepatoprotective activity was further confirmed by histopathological analysis. After sacrifice the liver tissue was used for histopathological analysis.

Antioxidant assays and lipid peroxidation studies of AEAC :

The liver homogenate (10% w/v) was prepared using PBS (pH 7.4) using a homogenizer and the supernatant were collected by centrifuging the samples at 5000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C. The activity of antioxidant enzymes was determined in the liver homogenate. Catalase (CAT) activity was measured according to the method of Beers and Sizer¹¹. CAT activity was expressed as μM of H₂O₂ consumed/min/mg protein. The superoxide dismutase

(SOD) activity was estimated by standard protocols of Marklund and Marklund¹². SOD activities of the samples were expressed as units/milligram protein. The levels of glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and glutathione-S-transferase (GST) were determined by the method of Rotruck *et al.*¹³ and Habig *et al.*¹⁴ respectively. Total protein content of the liver homogenate was estimated by kits from Euro Diagnostics Pvt. Ltd., India. The quantitative estimation of lipid peroxidation in the liver homogenate was determined according to the procedure of Hsu *et al.*¹⁵ by Thiobarbituric Acid Reactive Substances (TBARS) method. The levels of Malondialdehyde (MDA) were expressed as nM of MDA formed/mg protein.

Statistical analysis :

All the results were expressed as mean \pm S.D and the statistical analysis was performed using one way ANNOVA and Student Newman Keuls test. Statistically significant was considered as $p < 0.5$.

Results and discussion

Hepatoprotective activity :

The hepatoprotective and antioxidant role of aqueous extract of *Amorphophallus commutatus* var. *wayanadensis* were determined by estimating the levels of hepatic markers in the serum, histopathological analysis, antioxidant enzyme activity and lipid peroxidation. The levels of hepatic marker were significantly higher in the CCl₄ intoxicated group compared to the control group (Table 1). However, treatment with aqueous extract significantly decreased the levels of alkaline phosphatase (ALP), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT) by 216.57 ± 11.06 , 160.39 ± 11.24 and 109.05 ± 9.18 U/L respectively compared to 263.35 ± 7.86 , 314.45 ± 13.4 and 220.23 ± 7.55 U/L as in the CCl₄ intoxicated group. The levels of total bilirubin also in-

Table 1. Effect of aqueous extract of *Amorphophallus commutatus* var. *wayanadensis* on hepatic marker enzymes in mice models

Group	Treatment	AST (U/L)	ALT (U/L)	ALP (IU/L)	Total bilirubin (mg/dl)
Group I	Control	120.05 \pm 4.57	93.54 \pm 3.61	195.2 \pm 11.08	1.24 \pm 0.19
Group II	CCl ₄	314.45 \pm 13.45	220.25 \pm 7.55	263.35 \pm 7.86	4.47 \pm 0.14
Group III	Aqueous (200 mg/kg, p.o) + CCl ₄	220.95 \pm 1.63	162.57 \pm 2.67	276.45 \pm 9.71	2.61 \pm 0.14
Group IV	Aqueous (400 mg/kg, p.o) + CCl ₄	160.39 \pm 11.23	109.04 \pm 9.18	216.57 \pm 11.06	1.40 \pm 0.28
Group V	Silymarin (100 mg/kg, p.o) + CCl ₄	135.28 \pm 8.69	97.64 \pm 8.70	212.05 \pm 13.19	1.35 \pm 0.13

creased in the CCl₄ group were brought down by administration of 400 mg/kg aqueous extract. Carbon tetrachloride induced hepatic damage is a well established procedure to induce hepatotoxicity and antioxidant stress. CCl₄ when enters a biological system get converted to highly reactive CCl₃OO* by reacting with oxygen. These radicals generate oxidative stress condition and also cause lipid peroxidation by reacting with cell membrane. Loss of membrane integrity leads to the leakage of hepatic enzymes like alanine aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase, aspartate aminotransferase in the blood levels⁶. The elevated levels of hepatic marker in CCl₄ group from our results indicate the hepatic cellular damage caused by the free radicals. The aqueous extract is capable to bring the elevated levels of marker towards normal at 400 mg/kg administration. The hepatoprotective activity of the aqueous extract at 400 mg/kg is comparable to the standard silymarin at 100 mg/kg. Histopathological analysis also confirmed the hepatoprotective activity of AEAC (Fig. 1). Severe hepatic damages like mononuclear infiltration and necrosis was observed in the CCl₄ intoxicated groups.

Administration of AEAC showed lesser hepatic injury comparable to the standard drug silymarin.

Antioxidant enzymes are first line of defense in oxidative stress conditions, which protect the body from free radical mediated tissue injury. Superoxide dismutase and catalase plays major role in converting superoxide and hydrogen peroxide radicals respectively to non reactive end products. Glutathione peroxidase and glutathione-S-transferase are also involved in the detoxification of xenobiotic compounds to nontoxic compounds. Free radicals generated in the oxidative stress inactivated the activities of antioxidant enzymes⁷. Hence decreased levels of antioxidant enzyme activities are reported in the oxidative stress conditions. Our study also showed significant decrease in the antioxidant enzyme activities in the CCl₄ intoxicated group compared to the control group (Table 2). Treatment with AEAC showed dose dependent increase in the antioxidant enzyme activities. Non enzymatic antioxidant activity was evaluated by estimating the levels of total reduced glutathione. Treatment with AEAC increased the non-enzymatic antioxidant activity towards

Fig. 1. Histopathological analysis of liver sections. (A) Normal group; (B) CCl₄ intoxicated group; (C) aqueous extract 200 mg/kg; (D) aqueous extract 400 mg/kg; (E) silymarin 100 mg/kg.

Table 2. Effect of aqueous extract of *Amorphophallus commutatus* var. *wayanadensis* on CAT, SOD, GLU Px, GSH, GST activities and MDA levels in mice models

Group	Treatment	SOD	CAT	GLU Px	GSH	GST	LPO
I	Control	30.76 ± 2.39	156.3 ± 6.63	87.47 ± 1.18	22.86 ± 1.71	53.73 ± 2.23	2.29 ± 0.22
II	CCl ₄	11.08 ± 0.98	67.08 ± 2.92	54.83 ± 7.16	8.13 ± 1.87	31.14 ± 1.96	6.41 ± 0.73
III	Methanol (200 mg/kg) + CCl ₄	27.61 ± 4.93	92.79 ± 2.04	74.99 ± 5.54	15.28 ± 1.51	36.75 ± 1.69	4.90 ± 0.74
IV	Methanol (400 mg/kg) + CCl ₄	15.82 ± 1.61	139.1 ± 6.76	82.03 ± 7.1	21.61 ± 3.53	49.13 ± 0.75	2.96 ± 0.45
V	Silymarin (100 mg/kg) + CCl ₄	25.76 ± 3.39	140.5 ± 3.46	74.76 ± 2.23	20.14 ± 1.46	50.57 ± 6.22	2.8 ± 0.72

normal. AEAC at 400 mg/kg showed significant antioxidant activity comparable to the silymarin at 100 mg/kg. The present study revealed the antioxidant potential of AEAC against free radical mediated oxidative stress. Lipid peroxidation is considered as major indicator of oxidative stress mediated by free radicals. The free radical generated react with the lipid membrane and initiate cellular damage. The extent of lipid peroxidation was determined by the amount of MDA formed. The increased levels of MDA in the CCl₄ group were brought down towards normal in the AEAC (400 mg/kg) treated group. This shows the antioxidant activity of AEAC by scavenging the free radicals which helps in preventing the free radical mediated tissue injury.

Phytochemical analysis of the AEAC revealed the presence of saponins, glycosides, flavanoids and reduced sugars as the major phytoconstituents. Saponins were reported as potent hepatoprotective agent with antioxidant activity⁸. Our results also revealed the hepatoprotective and antioxidant activities, which might be attributed to the high saponin content in the samples.

Conclusion

The present study is the prior report on the hepatoprotective and antioxidant activity of aqueous extract of *Amorphophallus commutatus* var. *wayanadensis*. The aqueous extract showed potential antioxidant activity which protects the body from free radical mediated oxidative stress. Further studies are required to identify the bioactive compound responsible for the potential antioxidant activity.

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